

Wealth Treasury of Consciousness

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These are money makers and they will be sharing the way to break poverty and for you to enter into wealth and financial freedom. The challenging part that people have many times is understanding what does financial freedom look like?

It's a sin to keep the poverty lack mentality.

In an attempt to get money without service, is illegal to the law. They have to pay the price.

Whether you see this or not. A price will be paid.

Everything in the Earth is moving the money included in this , it is called currency.

One of the two things is happening, either you are creating or you are disintergrating. Getting richer or poorer its either one or the other.

If you fight for your limitations then Congratulations! You get to keep those valuable limitations. This is a fallacy.

Sharpen your learning to learn.

Money is a good servant but a bad master.

97% or 100 people never learn how to earn money /wealth. All the money you want.

What causes wealth? Money is in consciousness. This involves the mind, plan and blueprint.

WYTAYBA (What you think about you bring about) money wealth

Never say what the person wants talk about the consciousness of it . Example a great farmer speaks about seed sowing... hint hint.

Money is ink and paper... the breakdown

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Make the mental corrections,

change your paradigm of thinking

Change out people who have the lack, poverty mentality do it quickly. Health, wealth accounts and social circles. Change them out or just drop the people because its affecting your thought and mood or money and wealth accumulation.

sow crops good seeded quality crops of seed in fields pay

attention for location and season is very important. The farmer analogy.

Being broke is temporary, being poor is a mental condition.

Create a new system of treasury and find wells inside and outside. This can be information seminars financial game planning and goal setting.

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$$FG + E = I$$

Financial Goals+ Expenses=Income

(How much money do you want to have?)

To break the mindset of poverty it takes information and teaching. You **HAVE** to break it. Poverty is a great evil when you operate in it and does not produce joy wellness awesome days at all. Paint the picture, visualize and enter into that world.

People do not say, “I love being

BROKE!” No not a reality.

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M.S.I (Multiple Sources of Income)

People's ignorance of money is passed down from one generation to the other.

This has nothing to do with stocks, bonds, other means of investments, but more so has to do with the cause of money.

Grow or die it is one or the other. How this all works the thoughts, feelings, actions.

Money is an idea. Ink on paper is what it is. People still go bonkers because what it does for people.

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Don't feel bad or justify why you are successful.

The truth is rarely in the appearance of things.

People see, touch, taste, feel, actions lack and limitation.

Demand the abundant and the good life, nothing less.

Lack of prosperity consciousness is a major detrimental critical killer.

Much like a Phone and dial into frequency when we connect numbers connect through voice information and resources getting on the same page even from across the world. Same way, It's important to get on their frequency and vibration. People's thought is frequency and thought waves penetrate time and space.

We become what we think about. We have to tune into it. You have to really want it. Everything you need is here. Everything.

You need more money, but how much more is needed? You just have to know how to do it. Want is the only pre-requisite to get what you want. To make a decision. The irrevocable decision.

Money is in the air. When you are in harmony. Money flows where it is invited, and stays where it is welcome. Do not get angry any longer at money like it did something to you. A Lack of money does things life brings the on slot and money is a defense.

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The higher faculties (The Inside World)

1. Perception

2. Will

3. Mind

 4. Reason & Rationale Logic

5. Intuition

6. Memory $\frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$

7. Empathy

Flip your mind if you really want it. Change the channel of your mind and thoughts.

Paradigms are life the cyber control systems in a house dumb jobs, debt, stupid situations. Stuff like that.

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Countries and nations cultures work on a paradigm. Families....same way ..paradigm. Awareness is power. Results should always be under construction always improving.